

HISTORY OF MAHALLA COMMITTEES IN THE UZBEKISTAN SSR IN THE 1930S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

Sodiqov Furqat Fatulloyevich,
Asia International University,
Associate Professor, PhD

Abstract: The article analyzes the formation, legal basis, tasks and activities of mahalla committees in the Uzbek SSR in the 1930s. It also discusses elections to mahalla committees, their problems and shortcomings.

Keywords: local authorities, mahalla committee, local government, mahalla commissions, district soviet, city soviet, executive committees, village soviet.

After the formation of the Uzbek SSR, changes were made to local authorities. The traditional local authorities, the makhallas, were abolished in cities in 1924. However, the Soviet government, which faced difficulties in tax collection and other administrative issues in the makhallas, revived the makhallas as administrative agencies in cities. In English, mahalla means the same as the term neighborhood.

An important link in the local government bodies in the Uzbek SSR were the mahalla committees. On April 17, 1932, the regulation "On mahalla (district) committees in the cities of the Uzbek SSR" was approved [1,617-623]. In accordance with this regulation, mahalla committees were established instead of mahalla commissions, which had been operating on a public basis since 1924 without any remuneration. This regulation placed mahallas under the jurisdiction of city and district soviets, and also controlled the organization of their activities. In accordance with the regulation, mahalla committees were to implement general government decisions, collect state and local taxes and fees, carry out activities in the communal and cultural, social and economic spheres of urban development, as well as develop public initiative, maintain public order, and provide household services to the population.

According to the new regulations, members of the mahalla committees worked on a voluntary basis and did not receive any remuneration for their work. However, "in large mahallas, by decision of the general meeting of mahalla citizens and with the permission of the city council and the relevant district council, it was possible to include a secretary in the committee, who received a salary. The salary of the secretary of the mahalla committee and other expenses related to the work of the mahalla committee: stationery expenses, funds for maintaining the office room, insurance premiums were determined by the general meeting of mahalla citizens and subsequently approved by the city and relevant district councils[2.46].

Neighborhood committees were elected for a term of one year. They consisted of three people: a chairman, deputy chairman, secretary, and when permanent members left the composition, 2 candidates were elected in their place without elections and in turn. In large neighborhoods, it was allowed to increase the number of members of the neighborhood committee to 5 people and candidates to 3 people. According to the above Regulation, the main tasks of the neighborhood committees were:

to attract school-age children to schools, using all possible means, to ensure their participation in eliminating illiteracy of the population, as well as to organize material assistance to schools from the public;

to assist in the organization of craft artels, public enterprises, and soup kitchens, as well as to carefully approach the daily needs and requirements of working women;

to assist city and district soviets in registering and determining civil status acts by adopting measures to timely notify them of births, deaths, marriages, etc.[2.53].

In 1934, the territories of village soviets in the Uzbek SSR were revised. As a result, in 1931 there were 1,707 village soviets in the Uzbek SSR, while in 1934 their number was 1,246[3.396]. The reason for the reduction in the number of village soviets was their expansion. Small village soviets of two or more were merged into a single village soviet.

On December 20, 1936, the Organizational Department of the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of all the Union and autonomous republics distributed information "On the state of reception of workers and resolution of their written complaints". It also studied the situation in the Uzbek SSR, along with other republics, and acknowledged negative situations. In particular, it is reported that in the Andijan, Denov, Shakhrisabz, and Yakkabog district executive committees, workers' complaints were not even investigated, and several dozen complaints were piled up among various papers without being resolved. Among the 15 district executive committees studied in Uzbekistan, it is noted that the situation in the Termez district executive committee is relatively satisfactory. In the city of Kokand, they could not even find complaints. On the desk of Dementev, the head of the communal economy of the Kuybyshev district of Tashkent, there were 400 complaint applications awaiting their fate during 1933-1936 [4.154].

Neighborhood committees, which ensured the government's peace and acted as intermediaries between the people and the authorities, were constantly under the influence of communist ideology. This can be seen in the following examples.

Covering these events in their scientific and publicistic works, L. Levitin and D. Carlyle wrote: "The communist regime, which had destroyed many traditional Uzbek social structures, had to retreat in the struggle with the mahalla. It "did not get a tooth". The attack on the mahalla, which had been going on since the 1920s, was temporarily suspended by 1938"[5.38].

As for the fate of the mahalla committees, they were abolished on September 15, 1938 by a resolution of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR. This decision was explained by the fact that neighborhood committees were organized on the basis of old laws and regulations (as a community of residents living in the vicinity of a certain mosque), the frequent abuses of neighborhood committee members related to collecting various illegal fees from the population to support neighborhood committees, and the fact that the tasks previously performed by neighborhood committees should now be fully performed by district and city councils.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Polozhenie "O makhallinskih (kvartalnyx) komitetax v gorodakh Uzbekskoy SSR" // Sobranie uzakoneny i rasporyajeny raboche-dekhkanskoego pravitelstva Uzbekskoy Sovetskoy Sotsialisticheskoy Respubliki. April 17, 1932
2. Malikova G. Historical and legal issues of the development of the neighborhood institution. - Tashkent: New book, 2017.
3. Istorii sovetskogo gosudarstva i prava Uzbekistana: 1924-1937 gg. T. 2/ Otv. ed.: Kh. S. Sulaymanova and A. I. Ishanov. - Tashkent: Izdatelstvo AN UzSSR, 1963.
4. Haydarov M. The management system of the Soviet state in Uzbekistan: formation, stages and nature (1917-1941). - Tashkent: Abu press-consult, 2012.
5. Levitin L., Carlisle D. Islam Karimov - President of new Uzbekistan. 1996.

